

EFFICIENCY OF USING ALTERNATIVE ENERGY SOURCES

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Abstract: Energy prices are constantly rising, forcing payers to sigh heavily and think about increasing their revenues. Despite the achievements of civilization, there are many places outside the cities that are not supplied with gas, and in some places do not even have electricity. Where such an opportunity exists, the cost of installing the system sometimes does not correspond at all to the income level of the population. Not surprisingly, alternative energy with your own hands is of interest to both large and small rural homeowners and urban dwellers today. The whole world around us is full of energy, which is only present in the bowels of the earth. In school, in geography classes, we learned that the energy of wind, solar, flood, falling water, the earth's core, and other similar energy carriers can be used with high efficiency across the country and continents. However, alternative energy sources can also be used to heat a detached house. This article analyzes the feasibility and efficiency of using alternative energy sources.

Keywords: renewable energy sources, alternative energy, energy saving, energy efficiency of buildings.

Definition, potential and directions of development of alternative energy:

Small hydropower - power plants up to 10 MW, located on small rivers, canals, waterfalls. Technically, they are dams (cascades of dams) that provide a falling flow to the generator, or generators installed in series, lowered into a powerful water flow capable of providing sufficient kinetic energy to convert it into electrical energy.

Solar energy - the use of solar energy through:

- flat-plate collectors with glass or plastic coating and optical efficiency of at least 60-88%. They are mainly used for the production of hot water;

- modular solar receivers with a semiconductor coating of the required size and configuration. Used to generate electricity.

Wind energy - wind energy is used by means of wind turbines, representing a two-three-bladed power plant with a horizontal drive and a rotary (in the wind) device placed on the mast. Possibilities of use in the form of small cottage installations to the creation of large-scale wind parks.

Biomass - used through processing:

- fiber of wood origin, other plant organic matter and its derivatives for the production of motor and domestic fuels (bioethanol, biodiesel);
- recycling of household, municipal and industrial waste, as well as organic animal and human waste into biogas.

Geothermal - removal of heat from geothermal and volcanic activity through heat pumps.

The energy of the world's oceans - tidal and wave hydroelectric power plants.

Hydrogen energy is the production of hydrogen fuel by separating it from water and/or hydrocarbons (natural gas).

Alternative energy relies mainly on renewable energy sources (RES), which, depending on the application technology, are divided into traditional and non-traditional.

Traditional sources of RES include large-scale hydropower, as well as the use of traditional biomass (firewood, guzapoya, dung, etc.) through direct combustion of energy.

According to the methodology of the IEA (International Energy Agency), non-traditional RES include:

- hydropower resources of small hydropower up to 10 MW (i.e., except for large hydroelectric power plants), which convert the kinetic energy of water into electricity (water does not disappear anywhere);
- geothermal sources naturally coming from the earth's crust in the form of hot water, heat or steam;
- energy of sun;
- ocean energy (tidal, wave, currents, etc.);

- wind energy;
- industrial and municipal waste (solid, liquid, gaseous) capable of generating electricity when burned, biodegraded or otherwise processed;
- biomass of various origins, as a product of processing agricultural and forestry products, as well as plants specially cultivated for these purposes (annual reproduction of resources is possible).

In addition, in recent years, great attention has been paid to a new direction of non-traditional energy - hydrogen energy. Alternative energy also includes nuclear energy and thermonuclear fusion. In principle, alternative energy sources can include any, the most exotic sources that can replace traditional hydrocarbon raw materials.

The advantages of RES are the reproducible nature of the main resource for energy production, as well as high environmental friendliness.

Among the main disadvantages of RES are limited access to certain types of resources (not all countries have access to the sea, hydro resources of rivers, a sufficient level of winds, a sufficient number of sunny days a year, a sufficient amount of land and water resources to grow resources for bioenergy, etc.), as well as the still high cost of creating installations based on RES.

In addition, alternative sources based on natural processes (wind, sunny days, etc.) are not always associated in terms of the time of electricity production with the period of need for it, which makes these sources not sufficiently stable in terms of seasonality and rhythm of production, as well as requires their combination with traditional sources.

At the same time, the prospects for RES are associated with their sustainability in the long term, since their potential is huge and in the foreseeable future for a number of types is practically unlimited.

However, in the final balance of world energy consumption, the share of renewable energy is still about 13%, and, taking into account large hydroelectric power plants, it does not exceed 18-20%. At the same time, non-traditional energy sources account for only 2.5-3.5%.

World prospects for the development and promotion of alternative energy:

Alternative energy development strategies in developed and individual developing foreign countries are based on the understanding that:

- it is vital to create an alternative to exhaustible energy sources in advance. Their deficit in countries with these sources will increase in the period 2020-2030. with a sharp aggravation by 2050. This will lead to a sharp increase in energy prices in countries that do not have these resources and will jeopardize the development of national economies;
- alternative energy sources are the most environmentally friendly in terms of greenhouse gas emissions and become an essential condition for preventing a climate catastrophe;
- providing energy sources to settlements remote from cities depends almost entirely on the distribution of small alternative energy sources.
- The most significant areas where alternative energy sources could replace traditional hydrocarbon raw materials at the present time are the production of electricity and the production of motor fuel.

If we talk about the main directions of the priority, economically and environmentally justified introduction of renewable energy in Uzbekistan, then it is most expedient to do this where the economically determined tariff is high, and the possibilities for using renewable energy are quite good.

Let's start with the fact that these energy sources allow us to approach the production of electricity in a differentiated way: for a rural farm, you do not need to pull endless power lines - you can use biogas plants and windmills; for urban areas, small firms and enterprises, solar panels and collectors, plus the same biogas plants, are suitable; for large industrial enterprises - geothermal power plants, wind farms.

NRES also make it possible to regulate the power of the power plant without harming nature: increase or, if necessary, reduce it, dismantling redundant installations for further use (a dismantled solar battery can be sold, it can be installed for work elsewhere). The most common energy sources today do not allow this: at nuclear power plants there is a problem of catastrophic accidents, at hydroelectric power plants - the level of the reservoir changes, thermal power plants with their emissions and the use of fossil fuels are generally out of the

question in this case, even if waste is used as fuel - pollution is too high and from coal mining and CHP emissions.

This is not quite usual. Rather, quite unusual. However, if non-traditional renewable energy is not made commonplace today, then tomorrow, at best, we will again have to catch up with other countries in the production of environmentally friendly energy sources. And at worst... Man's intrusion into nature is as great as his ability to control natural processes and the consequences of anthropogenic impact is negligible - and a catastrophe can occur much earlier than coal, oil and gas run out.

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